

Thermoelectric Performance of CdS QDs Based Hybrid Nanocomposites

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Abstract:

Thermoelectric (TE) materials can produce direct electrical power from a formed temperature gradient (1). They are extremely reliable, 'fuel-free' solid-state devices for energy generation. TE devices can play an important role in energy harvesting and energy efficiency, however, their development is limited due to lack of high efficiency achieved from the currently available materials. Recent developments based on nanomaterials have shown dramatic improvements (by a factor 2 to 3) in the performance of TE devices. In the present study, we have prepared CdS QDs based ternary hybrid nanocomposites (RGO/CdS/PANI, RGO/CdS/PEDOT: PSS) and studied their thermoelectric behaviour. The electrical conductivity, seebeck coefficient and power factor of these nanocomposites were calculated with various loading of RGO-CdS nanocomposite in both PANI and PEDOT: PSS. The final RGO-CdS-PANI nanocomposites delivered high electric conductivity and power factor. The effective band alignment and decreased thermal conductivity in RGO-CdS-PANI nanocomposite resulted in p-type behaviour and high zT value.

Fig. a) SEM image of RGO-CdS-PANI nanocomposite and inset photograph of its re-dispersion in ethanol
b) Power Factor with filler concentration of RGO/CdS in RGO/CdS/PANI nanocomposite

Keywords: CdS quantum dots, Hybrid nanocomposites, Thermoelectric, Power factor.

Reference:

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